

Emergent spatial patterns can indicate upcoming regime shifts in a realistic model of coral community - Supplement 3: Supplementary Figure

Alexandre Génin^{*1,2}, Sergio A. Navarrete^{2,3,4}, Angeles Garcia-Mayor^{1,5}, Evie A. Wieters²

The American Naturalist

1 Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University, PO Box 80115, 3508 TC, Utrecht, The Netherlands.

2 Estación Costera de Investigaciones Marinas and Millenium Nucleus for Ecology and Conservation of Temperate Mesophotic, Reefs Ecosystems (NUTME), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Las Cruces, Chile.

3 Center for Applied Ecology and Sustainability (CAPES) and Coastal Socio-Ecological Millenium Institute (SECOS), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

4 Centro Basal COPAS COASTAL, Universidad de Concepción

5 Biodiversity, Ecology and Evolution Dept., Complutense University of Madrid, Spain

* Corresponding author: a.a.h.genin@uu.nl

Figure S3.1: Indicator trends along a gradient of increasing frequency of mortality events, for various values of d_0 (columns). Black lines indicate the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles of the computed indicator values, the ribbon the interquartile range, and the colored line the median. For each parameter combination, the distribution of values reflect 32 simulations.